

Nguyen Lo Trach's Innovative Ideology And Its Thoughts On The Renovation Process in Vietnam

Bui Thi Thu Hien

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 21, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 02, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Ideology, Social Life, National Development</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5062290</p>	<p><i>Nguyen Lo Trach was one of the initiations of the country's reform trend in Vietnam in the late nineteenth century. His systematic and comprehensive reform proposals cover all areas of social life: economic reformation, political reformation, cultural and educational reformation, military and diplomatic reformation... His reforming thought reflects a new vision and thinking to meet the requirements of national history, protection of sovereignty and national development. The article clarifies the content of reforming thought of Nguyen Lo Trach, from which we draw some lessons for the innovation in Vietnam nowadays with the article's approach based on the worldview and methodology of Marx's philosophy.</i></p>

Introduction

In order for the country to develop, the issue of innovation or reform is always an objective requirement of each country and nation. In each period, due to different historical conditions, the nature, content and methods of reform are different. Nguyen Lo Trach was born and raised under the reign of TuDuc (1848-1883) in the context of a serious social crisis: economic exhaustion, political security and political turmoil, military weakness, and being overlooked and invaded by the French colonialists. The country fell into the situation that "deep down inside, there was the people's unhappiness and the officialdom's evil "inside the suffering of the people and the corruption of mandarins, outside the situation of the West and the benefits of merchant ships" (Chuong&Giang, 1995: 142-143) which raised the issue of national renewal and renewal as an urgent requirement and was seen as a way, a new means of saving the country. Faced with that situation, with the spirit of patriotism, concern with the times, along with his talent and wisdom, Nguyen Lo Trach presented the king with proposals with profound innovation thought. Proposals such as "The Time of the Book (upper)", "The Time of the Book (the Lower)", "The Great Theory of the World"... have shown his innovative thought on the following aspects: economic reform, political innovation, cultural and educational reform, military and diplomatic innovation.

Nguyen Lo Trach was born on February 15, 1853 in Cam Lo (Quang Tri), from Ke Mon village, PhongDien district, ThuaThien province. His other name is Ha Nhan, his nickname is Ky Am. From an early age, he was famous for being intelligent, inquisitive, good at poetry and literature, but he did not take his career as his goal. Born in a family whose father is Doctor Nguyen QuocOai (passed in 1843) who used to hold the position of Senior Secretary of the Ministry of Justice and his father-in-law, Tran Tien Thanh is Senior Secretary of the foot-soldier, Nguyen Lo Trach has the conditions to study and interact with many hearings as well as new books of that time. In particular, he was exposed to the hearing of Nguyen Truong To, and the new books that Nguyen Truong To brought back from abroad. It helped him to understand more deeply the contemporary society as well as to be deeply aware of the enemy's aggressive intentions. On that basis, he proposed measures to comprehensively reform the country.

The research questions in this study will be:

Question 1: What is the content of Nguyen Lo Trach's innovative thought?

Question 2: What is the significance of Nguyen Lo Trach's innovative thought for the renovation process in Vietnam?

Literature Review

Regarding the topic of the article, there are two main works: *The History of Vietnamese thought* conducted by the Institute of Philosophy, consisting of 2 volumes, this is a fairly comprehensive, rich and profound work on the contents of Vietnamese thought. Male. In particular, related to the topic, in volume 2 of Le SyThang with the title *History of Vietnamese thought*, volume 2, Publishing House Social Sciences, Hanoi, 1997, clarifying the

problems of the process, as well as the characteristics of the reformist and conservative thought, the contents, values, and limitations of the innovation thought. This period through great thinkers, especially Nguyen Lo Trach.

The work *General History of Vietnam*, Complete Volume, by Truong HuuQuynh, Dinh Xuan Lam, Le Mau Han (editor), Education Publishing House, Hanoi, published in 2003; or *The History of Vietnam*, consisting of 2 volumes, of the Social Science Committee, Social Science Publishing House, Hanoi, 1971; in the book *The History of Vietnam*, Nguyen Quang Ngoc (editor), Education Publishing House, Hanoi, 2004... In these works, the authors have systematically researched and presented social life through the following fields: business economic, political, cultural, ideological... Vietnam period at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century; or the book *Vietnam historical events (1919-1945)*, by Duong TrungQuoc, Education Publishing House, published in 2002. This is a book in the Vietnam - historical events series of the Institute of History Organized, compiled and compiled by two volumes of the chronicle of the modern period of Vietnam's history (1858-1945), which presented an overview of Nguyen Lo Trach's outstanding contributions in the flow of people's history. Also in the same direction of studying historical events of Vietnam, that is the book *Following the National History* (volume 2), by Phan Van Quang, General Publishing House of Ho Chi Minh City. Ho Chi Minh, published in 2005; The content of this book is presented in the following categories: Vietnamese Tradition and Ethics, struggle movements, historical figures... in which the author presents and analyzes the views of the The patriotic thinkers of this period... went into the laboring masses and called for and awakened the compatriots against the imperialists and their henchmen, determined to build a culture of their own.

Along with the above research direction, *General History of Vietnamese Philosophical Thought*, Volume 1 edited by Nguyen Hung Hau, Publishing House. National University, Hanoi, 2002, the author presented an overview of the content of Nguyen Lo Trach's thought on economy, politics, culture, education...; *The history of Vietnamese thought* by Huynh Cong Ba, ThuanHoa Publishing House, Hue, in 2006, the work presented and analyzed the ideological content of thinkers in Vietnamese history, the work came to a conclusion. The core issue in the history of Vietnamese thought is "patriotism - democracy - compassion", to create profound views of the Vietnamese people.

The work *The development of thought in Vietnam from the nineteenth century to the August Revolution*, volume 1, by Tran Van Giau, Publishing House. Social Science, Hanoi, 2003, analyzed the Vietnamese society facing three major problems of the times: "righteous path" and "evil religion", neo-conservative or conservative? war or draw?

General History of Vietnam, (Complete, Education Publishing House, Hanoi, 2003), by Truong HuuQuynh, Dinh Xuan Lam, Le Mau Han (Editor). In this work, the authors have researched and presented in a fairly systematic way about social life such as economy, politics, culture, ideology,... of the period from the end of the nineteenth century to the beginning of the 20th century. Research on the development of Vietnamese thought in this period also includes the work *The development of thought in Vietnam from the 19th century to the August Revolution*, consisting of 3 volumes, National Political Publishing House, Hanoi, 1996 by Tran Van Giau. This is a massive research work referring to the transformation process of three ideologies that follow each other, alternate and struggle with each other, that is: feudal ideology; bourgeois ideology; proletarian ideology.

In addition, it is also necessary to mention the work of *Vietnamese Thought from the 15th to the 19th century*, by Doan Chinh, National Political Publishing House - Truth, published in 2012 has researched, commented and assessed quite deeply and accurately about the ideological content, characteristics and meaning of his thoughts. Nguyen Lo Trach's reformist ideas; Cao Mai Chuong: *Nguyen Lo Trach - Reformer, poet*, Literature Review, No. 3, 2000. Doan Le Giang, *Nguyen Lo Trach - testimony and poetry*, Publishing House. Social Sciences, 1995. Nguyen Van Huyen, *Nguyen Lo Trach and Di Thao*, Publishing House Social Sciences, 1995.

However, at present, there has not been a complete and profound study of the thought of Nguyen Lo Trach and its significance for Vietnam today. These are valuable documents for the author to inherit in the research paper.

Research Method

Method and Data

The research is based on the worldview and the methodology of Marxist philosophy, and at the same time uses specific research methods such as analysis - synthesis, logic - history, deductive - inductive, compare - contrast and textual methods to study and present the content of the article according to the set purpose.

Results and Discussion

The content of Nguyen Lo Trach's innovative thought

Answer the pressing problems of Vietnamese social history at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, which is the requirement to liberate the Vietnamese people and nation from domination, oppression and exploitation of the feudal colonial regime, on the basis of inheriting the humanistic values in the historical, ideological and cultural traditions of the Vietnamese nation, along with the selective absorption of the humanistic spirit in the Vietnamese culture. Eastern and Western ideology and culture, views expressing human values in PhanBoi Chau's thought have been formed and developed. Marx and Engels, said: "The ideological echo of the life process" (Marx & Engels, 1995: 38) and is the most beautiful crystallization of Nguyen Lo Trach's affection, intelligence, spirit. Contents of Nguyen Lo Trach's thought expressed:

Firstly, about economics. Nguyen Lo Trach advocated planting and trading to create food and financial resources, contributing to building internal resources and stabilizing people's lives. This innovative thought comes from his assessment of the economic situation of our country under the Nguyen Dynasty, which is "bad harvest due to epidemics, then opium, counterfeit money circulated, and people's strength was depleted day by day" (Chuong&Giang, 1995: 112). Therefore, the land is not enough to support the farmers, more debt, piled taxes and besides, the luxury and frivolity of the mandarins make the country's finance and military decline. The government's policy of "emphasis on farming and limited the trade", "closed doors and ports" not dealing with the West partly because of vigilance, partly because of conservatism and self-defence, also strangled the country's commerce industry. Faced with that situation, in order to strengthen the country's economy, Nguyen Lo Trach advocated "planting" and "trading" on the basis of self-reliance. The process of reclaiming and setting up hamlets under the Nguyen dynasty helped the Nguyen Dynasty to partially restore the country's agriculture, but since the French's invasion, the people were displaced, and the fields became desolate in many places. Based on the actual conditions of the country, in the areas of TuyenQuang, Lang Son, Son Tay, BacNinh..., which are deserted areas, widely favorable for cultivation, Nguyen Lo Trach advocated the implementation of "using soldiers for farming" to reclaim land and establish plantations. According to him, the court "sends a general to lead several thousand troops, choose a fertile land to cultivate, there will definitely be results" (Chuong&Giang, 1995: 113). In addition to the main army, it is necessary to recruit more volunteers and have a clear division of work: "The elite, healthy group will be retained to work on patrol. The rest are sent to work in the fields" (Chuong&Giang, 1995: 112). With this number of troops, divided into teams, each team of 50 people, with a captain and a secretary, each person receives three acres of field, each team receives 150 acres. He planned the effectiveness of this policy: "Each acre of field is only collected 10 quintals, the rest is divided into 10 parts: one part is stored as seed for next year; 4 parts divided by team (captain), secretary; 5 parts to be divided among the soldiers so that they all share in the benefits" (Chuong&Giang, 1995: 113). With such calculations, he believes that the amount of food produced not only meets the needs of society, buys necessary things and has leftovers to accumulate: "So, with 50 people, but receiving 150 acres of fields, every year there is 1500 quintals of rice. If there are 10,000 people, about 150,000 boxes of rice, each year there is a surplus of 150,000 quintals of rice. If 50,000 people are planted as plantations, and the field is not less than 150,000 acres, will it not be less than 150,000 quintals a year?" (Chuong&Giang, 1995: 114). Although this calculation was still subjective, it was suitable with the large land conditions, abundant human resources, relatively favorable weather... of Vietnam at that time and it expressed the will of innovation of Nguyen Lo Trach.

To develop the country's economy, Nguyen Lo Trach also advocated combining plantation work with expanding trade. Because, with the ability to think sharp ahead of the times, Nguyen Lo Trach is aware that times are different. Along with the progress of mankind is the scientific - technical revolution that has linked countries together, no country can develop if it is separated from its relationship with other nations and peoples. At the same time, stemming from the condition that our country has a rich source of salt but is exclusively managed and distributed by the state, he advocated exporting salt abroad to benefit the country and people. He pointed out: "Now let's appoint an official to take care of the transportation of salt to exchange with Guangxi and Yunnan regions. Every year I will get no less than a few tens of thousands of taels of silver" (Chuong&Giang, 1995: 115-116). Or "Try to take the public capital of tens of thousands of taels of silver, and give it to a diligent mandarin to use ships to go back and forth to trading countries" (Chuong&Giang, 1995: 116). Thus, expanding trade not only brings benefits to the country but also has the opportunity to exchange, learn from other countries, acquire their technology to improve production techniques. In the context that the Nguyen kings and mandarins carried out a "seclusion of the port", closing the door to the outside, Nguyen Lo Trach's idea of opening the door to trade could be considered a bold thought.

Secondly, about politics. Nguyen Lo Trach advocates political reform to develop the country; must reform and build political lines, taking struggle as a long-term strategy, based on defense and reasonable harmony. The policy of governing the country depends on the socio-economic conditions of each country, but when it is born, it affects the socio-economic conditions that gave birth to it. Deeply aware of this issue and with a keen political vision, Nguyen Lo Trach advocates that it is necessary to "correct" politics - education on the basis of making the country richer and stronger. To do that, the court first needed to "locate" itself, determine the "position" between us and the enemy, and only on that basis could an appropriate "institution" be established. In which, he pointed out: "We have to sincerely give up the vanity that we don't have, define our real scope, make a clear

institution, others are not allowed to interfere in power and authority. Then, above and below, in one heart, discuss together" (Chuong&Giang, 1995: 142). Nguyen Lo Trach is also very dialectical when he thinks that in order to preserve the country, not only can we discuss but also need to come up with specific and practical action measures, but most importantly, find out the causes of weakness in order to have solutions to overcome them by an appropriate treatment, just like "a physician must know the cause of the disease and then treat that cause, then the disease will be cured" (Chuong&Giang, 1995: 142). He determined that the cause of the chaos and turbulence of society at this time was because we had not found a correct way and means of saving the country. In the situation that our country is now in a mess, "there are not only external enemies but also internal turmoil", outside the enemy attacks, but our country is weak, unable to resist; Inside, the corruption of the bureaucracy is rampant, finding a plan is nothing but three things: fight, defend, and détente. In dealing with the relationship between these three things, if Nguyen Truong To advocates détente, Nguyen Lo Trach thinks that détente is only a temporary strategy. Because he was aware that the French colonialist's invasion plot was not an immediate action; not because our country is weak, but because they "gain great profits". For a long time, they hid under the guise of "civilization" to suppress, plunder, exploit and oppress other countries with the scheme of "silkworms eating mulberry leaves" and if we keep shrinking and afraid we will be bound by them. But to fight, you need a strong enough force. Therefore, according to him, conciliation is to build strength, build forces, prepare when the time comes to win, not conciliation is to sit idly and expect the situation to turn around. For him, fighting is still a long-term strategy even though it's very difficult, but with one heart, determination will be achieved. Fighting, defense, and détente must be used flexibly and at the right time, which will determine the success or failure of the national defense strategy. At the same time, it is necessary to seize the opportunity, in which, expanding trade with foreign countries is considered by Nguyen Lo Trach as a good opportunity to strengthen the country's economy, learn from their experiences and also an opportunity to consider the enemy's situation and plan how to respond. More specifically, he proposed innovative measures in terms of education, in which he focused on learning and absorbing Western science and technology. It can be seen that, up to this time, the application of Western scientific and technological achievements is not new, but under Vietnamese society it is completely strange. While contemporaneous with him, the confucianists, under the influence of the "Four Books, the Five Classics, and the First King of the Law", considered Western science and technology as "technique", "artisan" and then despised, even expressing displeasure and protest, Nguyen Lo Trach determined: "The current urgent task, of course, cannot delay technical learning" (Chuong&Giang, 1995: 113). Although his reformist thought on education, sending people abroad to study industry is considered a "fantasy" at the moment, but with a far-sighted vision, he determined: "going to school today, although it is not practical for urgent work while defending the country at this time, it is not a failure to learn to have a basis when it is time to do it" (Chuong&Giang, 1995: 136). He cited a series of countries from England, France, Prussia to Russia, Japan, and even China, which are becoming stronger by applying scientific and technical achievements to production. For our country, he determined, "I am in a situation where I put a fire under a pile of firewood, which is a ten-year plan, and I know it's not practical. But if you want the effect to be quick, it won't be of great benefit..." (Chuong&Giang, 1995: 117). If we want to get rid of the current state of chaos and confusion, we cannot wait for foreign help but need to create strength to be self-reliant and self-governing.

Third, about the military. Nguyen Lo Trach advocated for the military, to build a strong army to fight the enemy, and at the same time, strictly re-recruiting soldiers, training elites; consolidating military force must be paralleled with equipping modern weapons and preferential treatment for soldiers. This renewal policy came from the reality of our military at that time. First of all, according to Nguyen Lo Trach, although our army is large but not strong, "some people are old, some are as young as children"; Those who join the army are not only not exempt from the immunities, but also do the errands and have to practice at the same time. In addition, they are not interested in both material and spiritual life, "as the monthly salary is too low, the salt and fish sauce is not provided, they have to contribute" (Chuong&Giang, 1995: 117), the risk of disease is high. It shows that our military strength is very weak, while comparing the relationship between our forces and the enemy: "our ships are not as sturdy as theirs; in terms of fighting methods, we are not as powerful as them, and the army and finances are both miserable" (Chuong&Giang, 1995: 88). Therefore, Nguyen Lo Trach advocated that the army should be consolidated in time. According to him, soldiers need to be elite and, therefore, first of all need to be strictly selected: "It is better to have one man who can use one than to have ten men who cannot use one" (Chuong&Giang, 1995: 119). At the same time, it is necessary to have a good treatment regime for those who join the army, to treat them with trust and honesty, and to give them a salary according to their rank. He said that the strength of the army is not only in numbers but also in weapons and in fact also proves that weapons are not as sharp as giving troops to the enemy. While the enemy is equipped with modern weapons, our weapon is still outdated, even though there are flintlock guns, it is "clumsy, heavy, slow, difficult to carry, with a slanted trigger hole, ash and Ammunition mixed up, when in battle, they had to turn the barrel back to fill it, and shot incorrectly" (Chuong&Giang, 1995: 119). Therefore, in order to strengthen the army, according to him, it is necessary to "give up all old guns and buy new Western guns" - firearms (rifles), even though this purchase compares with the economic conditions of our country. This is a very difficult problem, but if we don't solve it,

the army will not be strong, and no matter how many we have, no matter how strong we are, we can't stand the enemy.

Nguyen Lo Trach also proposed to use diplomacy in defending the country, in which, must open the door to exchange with other countries, combine external aid with building and developing internal resources on the basis of self-reliance. If the contemporary rulers advocated "closed-door seclusion", did not care or did not see the importance of diplomacy in defending the country, then Nguyen Lo Trach realized that "diplomacy is very necessary and important". Because, according to him, the times are different, big and small countries meet, converge, and do business. Therefore, on the one hand, it is necessary to strengthen the internal strength of the country, on the other hand, it is necessary to take advantage of cooperation with other countries to understand the enemy, find allies, and take advantage of opportunities to restore the country. He said: "Lost in the east, will recover in the west, but the feet do not step out of the yard, how to know the situation to seize the opportunity" (Chuong&Giang, 1995: 124). However, the unique point in Nguyen Lo Trach's diplomatic thought is that, relying on external power is only a supplement to our shortcomings; the internal strength of the nation is still decisive. He pointed out: "If you want to rely on foreign countries, you must first become independent. The so-called help is only specially used to supplement where our strength is not enough, not completely rely on other people's strength to keep the country" (Chuong&Giang, 1995: 124). Thereby, it can be seen that if the country wants to enlist foreign help, it needs to be self-reliant. It can be said that the idea of self-reliance, which is the red thread that runs through all of his thoughts, whether in economics, politics, society or military and diplomacy, Nguyen Lo Trach has clearly expressed his ideology of self-reliance. It is their own strength to build and maintain the country. Among those ideas, Nguyen Lo Trach pays great attention to the method of conduct. For him, the implementation method is the decisive factor for the success or failure of the reform, if there is a right path but an inappropriate method of implementation, it will not bring results and cannot achieve the goal.

Fourthly, about education. Nguyen Lo Trach proposed innovative measures in terms of education, in which he focused on learning and absorbing "forte talents" and techniques of the West. It can be seen that, up to this point, the application of Western scientific and technical achievements is nothing new, but under Vietnamese society it is completely strange. While at the same time as him, the Confucianists, influenced by Confucian thought, considered Western science and technology as "artisan" and "artisan" and despised and even expressed their displeasure. When protesting, Nguyen Lo Trach determined: "the current urgent task, of course, cannot delay technical learning" (Chuong&Giang, 1995: 133). Although his reformist thought on education and sending people abroad to study industry is considered a "fantasy" at the moment, but with a far-sighted vision, he determined: "going to school today" Although it is not practical for urgent work in this time of rescue, it is not a failure to learn to have a basis when it is time to do it" (Chuong&Giang, 1995: 136). He cited a series of countries from England, France, Prussia to Russia, Japan, and even China, which are becoming stronger by applying scientific and technical achievements to production. For our country, he determined, "I am in a situation where I put a fire under a pile of firewood, which is a ten-year plan, and I know it's not practical. But if you want the effect quickly, there is no great benefit..." (Chuong&Giang, 1995: 117); If we want to get rid of the current state of chaos and confusion, we cannot wait for foreign help but need to create strength to be self-reliant and self-governing.

Thus, facing the dangerous fate of the nation, Nguyen Lo Trach proposed to reform the country in all fields of economy, politics, culture - education, military, diplomacy,... along with solutions very practical. Nguyen Lo Trach's renovation thought is a demonstration of self-reliant strength in national reform and renewal, a harmonious combination between temporary and long-term strategies, and at the same time it shows the ability to response of a progressive thinker's thinking to the change of the times. His proposals were considered "too high" and unused, but they reflected the pressing need for the way of defending the country as well as the objective requirements of reform and renewal of the country at that time: if you wanted to preserve and develop the country, there was only one way that was to reform the country. If you insist on keeping the "old ways", sooner or later it will lead to failure and loss of the country. Currently, thanks to the comprehensive renovation of the country, our country has come out of the socio-economic crisis, has undergone fundamental and comprehensive changes, creating new development steps to help the country become more and more stable, overcome difficulties, shorten the distance with countries in the region and integrate into the common development of the world. The economy has overcome many difficulties and challenges, the scale and potential has been increased; Education and training, science and technology, culture, etc. There has been a development in culture, society, health; political – social is stable; national defense and security are enhanced; external relations and international integration are becoming more and more extensive and effective. Vietnam's international position and prestige continues to be enhanced.

Nguyen Lo Trach's innovative thought for the renovation process in Vietnam

In the process of innovation and international integration, besides opportunities and advantages, Vietnam still has many obstacles, challenges and difficulties, which are: "he economy has overcome many difficulties and challenges, the scale and potential has been increased... Education and training, science and technology, culture, society, health have developed... politics - society stable association; national defense and security are

strengthened... external relations and international integration are becoming more and more extensive and effective. Our country's international position and reputation continues to be enhanced" (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2016:14-15), however "the situation in the world and in the region is very complicated; Slow recovery of the world economy; political crisis in many places and countries; increasingly fierce competition among major countries in the region; complicated developments in the East Sea..." (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2016:13).

Therefore, it is necessary to study innovation thought in history in general, including Nguyen Lo Trach's innovation thought so that from the contents of Nguyen Lo Trach's innovation thought, some lessons can be drawn from the experience. Experience for the current national renewal process:

Firstly, it is necessary to show the strength of self-reliance in the renewal of the country. In economics, politics, education, military or diplomacy, Nguyen Lo Trach clearly expressed the idea of self-reliance, relying on his own internal strength to build and defend the country. If you need outside support, it's just an addition to your current inadequacies. Affirming national independence is a key condition for all actions of the nation.

Secondly, the country must be completely renewed in all aspects of economy, politics, culture - education, military, diplomacy, ect. to be self-reliant and defend the country, it must be renovated, it must be repaired in time all aspects of social life, and areas of social life are closely related to each other as each part of a complete organism. If the economy is poor and exhausted, political becomes instability, education and military becomes weakness. Therefore, economic reform will serve as the basis for stable politics, education, and strong military; On the contrary, political reform and reduction of cumbersome administrative procedures will create a favorable environment for economic development. In other words, reforming on one side will be a precondition, a condition for innovation on the other side and vice versa.

Thirdly, the renewal of the country must be done by concrete and practical measures. Nguyen Lo Trach presented his renovation ideas not in the form of a comprehensive reform system but with timely response solutions to save the nation from foreign invasion. His whole thought of reforming the country comes from objective and practical requirements and they solve the requirements and problems posed by reality. Depending on different historical periods and different fields, there are different innovative solutions. However, in general, innovation is based on self-reliance, steadfastly pursuing the goal of national independence, and at the same time actively integrating and absorbing the achievements of human civilization.

Conclusion

The history of Vietnamese philosophical thought in the process of formation and development has left profound imprints, creating spiritual values and making great contributions to the history of nation building, defense and land development country of the Vietnamese nation, contributing to enriching the theoretical treasure of mankind. It can be affirmed that the victory of the Vietnamese revolution today is the result of the process of drawing experience, inheriting and promoting previous historical values. The study of Nguyen Lo Trach's reforming thought will make a great contribution to the study of the history of Vietnamese thought in general, and a historical lesson for summarizing the practice to carry out the current innovation process in Vietnam.

Acknowledgement

We would like to express the anonymous research participants for their willingness to have taken part in this study. Additionally, our sincere gratitude should go to other relevant parties who have given comments and supported us during our study. Without their unconditional help and support, we would have never been able to finish this study.

References

- Ba, C.H. (2006). *History of Vietnamese thought*. Hue:ThuanHoa.
- Chung, V.T &Chinh, D. (2005). *The turning of Vietnamese thought in the late 19th century and early 20th century*. Hanoi: National politics.
- Chinh, D., &Thin, D.P. (2007). *The process of transforming Vietnamese political thought at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century through character symbolism*. Hanoi: National politics.
- Chinh, D. (2012). *History of Oriental Philosophy*. Hanoi: National politics.
- Chuong, M.C., &Giang, D.L. (1995). *Nguyen Lo Trach – testimony and poetry*, Hanoi: Social Sciences.
- Communist Party of Vietnam. (2016). *Documents of the 12th National Congress of Deputies*. Hanoi: The National Political Publishing House.
- Huyen, V.N. (1995). *Nguyen Lo Trach and herbs*. Hanoi: Social Science
- Lam, X.D. (Editor, 2006). *Outline of Vietnamese history*, vol 2. Hanoi: Education.
- Luc, T.N. (1997), *Perception of the Meiji renewal of Vietnamese revolutionary thinkers at the end of the 19th century – the case of Nguyen Truong To and Nguyen Lo Trach*. Journal of Historical Research.
- Giang, D.L. (1995). *Nguyen Lo Trach - testimony and poetry*. Hanoi: Social Science

- Giau, V.T. (1996). *The development of thought in Vietnam from the nineteenth century to the August Revolution, vol. 1: Feudal ideology and its failure to historical tasks*. Hanoi: National politics.
- Giau, V.T. (1997). *The development of thought in Vietnam from the nineteenth century to the August Revolution, volume 2: Bourgeois ideology and its inability to face historical tasks*. Hanoi: National politics
- Marx, K. & Engels, F. (1995). *Entire episode*, vol. 3. Hanoi: National politics.
- Ngoc, H., & Hoa, N.T. (2005). *Innovation trend, renewal movement, innovation career (from the middle of the 19th century to the end of the 20th century)*. Danang.
- Thang, S.L. (1997). *History of Vietnamese thought*, Volume 2. Hanoi: Social Science, Hanoi, 1997.
- Thang, Q.N. (2005). *Reform movement and typical faces*. Hanoi: Culture – Information.
- Thuan, T. (2014). *Attitudes of Vietnamese scholars in the East-West contact period (from the 17th century to the early 20th century)*. Ho Chi Minh City.
- Xuan, V.N. (1995). *Reform movement*. Danang.

Author Information

Dr. Bui Thi Thu Hien

Vietnam National University - Ho Chi Minh City,
Vietnam
